

emeritus

FIGHTING AGAINST
WASTE CRIMES

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PROJECT OVERVIEW

EMERITUS Project

Environmental protection is currently jeopardised by unregulated criminal activities and asymmetrical enforcement of measures among European Union Member States. **Environmental crimes**, such as the **discharge of substances** into the air, water and soil, as well as the **shipping and trafficking of waste and hazardous materials**, have enormous impacts on the climate, human health and the environment. However, these crimes are still considered highly profitable for criminals since most feature relatively low risks of detection and penalties for the perpetrators, given the complexity of preventing criminal wrongdoings and delivering distinct proofs to law courts to punish the authors.

The term **'waste crime'** encompasses a wide range of illegal activities throughout the entire waste management cycle, i.e., production, storage, transportation, disposal, and reuse. Waste crime includes **waste trafficking, waste dumping, the mismanagement of waste and water, and air pollution**. "Recently, INTERPOL estimated that the average profit margin for pollution-related crimes was significant, at \$19.6 million per crime (INTERPOL, 2022)." On the other hand, environmental investigative teams in law enforcement agencies (LEAs) have limited specialised resources and technical devices.

Despite the growing recognition of waste crime as a serious global issue, there is a notable lack of empirical research exploring how law enforcement investigations can be improved. Technologies can offer a range of solutions for enhancing the detection, investigation and prosecution of waste crimes, which can, in turn, increase the risk associated with engaging in such activities. Valuable yet limited forensic literature identified the potential for a range of technologies to support waste crime investigation (Alderuccio et al., 2019). Drones are one of the main technologies the literature recognises that can help fight crimes like waste dumping, water pollution, and the mismanagement of industrial waste sites (Mager & Blass, 2022), with several advantages in the investigation procedure (Sliusar et al., 2022). Satellites also offer two distinct advantages for improving the investigation of waste crimes: time series images over an area of interest provided through repositories and rapid reconnaissance of large areas using multiple sensors (Karimi et al., 2023). Recent developments in satellite technology have also increased their potential application to waste crime investigations sevenfold.

PROJECT OVERVIEW

EMERITUS as funded project

In this framework, EMERITUS aimed at laying the foundations for a **new generation of technological tools at the service of LEAs/Border Guards (BGs)** while actively empowering them to use such tools at national and cross-border level, while facilitating collaborative operations and networking in this domain. In details, the aim of the EMERITUS project is to realize and implement a **protocol** for effective environmental crime investigation, leveraging on the integration of **innovative monitoring and analysis technologies**, and on a complementary **training programme** aimed at fostering Environmental enforcement authorities' (e.g. LEAs, BGs) intelligence and investigation capabilities at national level and cross-border level.

New technologies such as satellites, drones and deep learning/AI (and data merger with other datasets) are capable of providing synoptic high content data coverage of large areas of land or water, regularly and irrespective of inaccessibility or hazard. These can offer potential powerful solutions to the above issues surrounding the identification of environmental crime. However, LEAs/BGs are not always aware of these latest R&I and industry developments, and also require better evidence of their utility. The ambition of EMERITUS has been to explore and demonstrate how these technologies could improve the efficiency of **environmental crime detection**, intelligent risk profiling to reflect resources, reduce the risk for operators and provide a deterrent for offending.

Introduction

The purpose of this final report is to provide an overview of the development process of the EMERITUS project and the outcomes it has achieved. The report outlines the project's conceptual framework and the rationale behind its creation, the methodology through which the project was developed, the stakeholders involved, its initial objectives, and the results obtained.

Additionally, this report discusses the lessons learned throughout the project management of EMERITUS. This analysis facilitates a holistic understanding of the impact generated by the project. It also enables the identification of the different stages of EMERITUS—from its inception and planning to the digital tools, training programmes, and other resources provided to

Border Guards and Law Enforcement Authorities. These tools and training were designed to address the aforementioned environmental crimes and improve investigation protocols. The project also established a Community of Practice (CoP) that contributed to the continuous improvement of the project, integrating expert opinions on the various tools and aspects of the platform.

The report concludes with a roadmap ahead, regarding the future of EMERITUS as a digital tool for monitoring environmental crimes related to waste management, alongside the sustainability of the overall results, including the platform, training initiatives, and the policy recommendations derived from the project.

PROJECT OVERVIEW

Consortium overview

LEAs & BORDER GUARDS

TECHNOLOGY PROVIDERS

SECURITY SPECIALISTS

TRAINING & CO-CREATION

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The active engagement of practitioners, the ultimate users and beneficiaries of the project's results, are crucial to ensure that said results reflect the actual needs of the operators and that are actually deployable in relevant environments. To this end, the project's Consortium adopted 'co-creation' as a methodological approach to be implemented throughout key phases: requirement definition and design of the investigation protocols. For requirements, the participation of LEAs and BG authorities allowed for understanding their needs to define a roadmap. In the case of protocols, it actively engaged LEAs and BG authorities in the design and development of the protocol. Consequently, this would increase their awareness and sense of ownership. To achieve this, EMERITUS adopted the design thinking methodology.

Design thinking is an iterative process for human-centered innovative design of products and solutions, whose most known version was defined by the Stanford Institute of Design. This methodology seeks to understand user-perspective and needs in order to challenge typical assumptions and define original human-centered solutions, and it encompasses 5 (non-linear and iterative) steps, namely: **1) Empathize, 2) Design, 3) Ideate, 4) Prototype and 5) Test.** Each step has specific aims and corresponding tools/approaches. The design thinking methodology has already been adopted in different application areas in the field of security and its use has been extensively analysed by scholars. For the purposes of EMERITUS, the design thinking methodology has been adapted as follows:

EMPHATIZE

Analysis of current investigation practices, best practices collection and through user-needs analysis, getting to the initial elaboration of personas that will be progressively updated along the process.

DESIGN

This phase allowed to synthesize and select a set of common needs in collaboration with the partner LEAs/BGs. The direct interaction and consultation allowed to gather relevant insights on the needs, type of solution desired and type of solution acceptable

IDEATE

Collaborative elaboration of potential solutions involving both end-users and technological experts.

PROTOTYPE

Progressively accurate prototypes of both the investigation protocol and the EMERITUS platform have been created and presented to both partners LEAs/BGs and to the wider CoP to gather feedbacks and suggestions in an agile logic (several loops of prototyping, release, feedback, update).

TEST

Putting the investigation protocol and the EMERITUS platform in operation in controlled environments, providing end-users with the competences to operate them (via the dedicated training) and observing the results, behaviours, and gaps experienced and extracting indications for refinement and scale up.

KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

Digital platform

The EMERITUS project aimed, on the one hand, to enable access to **evidence-based intelligence**, creating an integrated picture on environmental crimes, patterns/behaviours of their perpetrators and relevant connections with any other form of organized crime, as well as facilitating cross-country interforce cooperation among LEAs/BGs and other relevant operators. On the other hand, the project aimed to improve the **effectiveness of investigation** operations by exploiting State of the Art technologies to map waste disposal and storage sites, identify pollutants or other illegally discharged substances, detect wastes, collect evidence in lawful court-proof manner, and enhance contrast of environmental crime-involved organised networks.

EMERITUS lays the foundations of a new generation of technological tools orchestrated via a single-entry point platform at the service of LEAs and BGs to improve detection and proof collection capabilities against waste-related environmental crimes.

OBJECTIVES

Strengthening cross-border vision providing an intelligence picture beyond border.

Creation of an integration layer scalable by design to allow the integration of other data sources and technologies.

Collection of lawful court-proof of crime evidence.

KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

Digital platform

Waste from space evidence (Satellite imagery based)

When a project utilizes the 'WasteFromSpace' service over a defined geographic area, the designated service provider, conducts a comprehensive analysis of the specified region. This process identifies and maps a series of locations, termed 'Waste Sites,' which are potential illegal waste disposal sites.

Remote drone control

Provides semi-automated control of drones, for end users who lack the training required to operate drones themselves. This functionality allows to remotely control a drone from a PC connected to the platform, as well as to plan automatic mission for individual or coordinated drones.

Waste trafficking detection

Provides detection of sites involved in waste trafficking through the analysis of optical satellite imagery and volumetric estimation.

Water pollution detection

Provides real-time warnings about potential contamination events, along with estimated metrics including timing and severity.

3D mapping

This service generates a 3D point cloud of a (limited) area of interest, based on drone photogrammetric survey or lidar terrestrial survey. In the former case, the output will include also a Digital Surface Model (DSM) and an orthoimage of the area of interest. This is relevant for the services Landfill Waste Classification, Waste from Space and Waste Trafficking Detection.

Waste site expert report

Provides expert analysis of a site under investigation, through the analysis of VHR optical satellite data, thermal anomaly data, and evidence drawn from other services. Upon submission, the partner company receives an email notification containing key details of the waste site, such as its coordinates, ID, and other relevant information. The email also provides comprehensive instructions on how and where to upload the expert report.

Additionally, EMERITUS Platform provides a number of services related to the notification of the environmental crimes, the safety of the data gathered through the platform and access to information, such as:

DIGITAL PLATFORM

EMERITUS service sensors

KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

Investigation protocol

The EMERITUS project created a series of Investigation Protocols aimed at helping to tackle environmental crimes through the services provided on the EMERITUS platform. The crime-based investigation protocols align with the crimes targeted by EMERITUS use cases of waste dumping, water pollution, waste trafficking, and illegal waste storage. This aims to provide **practical guidance** on how to utilise EMERITUS technological solutions and where to implement them in particular waste crime investigations. In this way, the Integrated Investigative Protocol

is grounded in the practical everyday reality of using these technologies in specific waste crime investigations.

Each of the four protocols consists of a series of stages that describe step by step how to handle each crime and which EMERITUS services are applicable at each stage. While the steps are similar across protocols, the tools differ depending on the specific needs of the BGs and LEAs, as identified through the co-creation process. The overall concept of the Investigation protocols covers the following phases:

Preliminary phase

DETECTION/SUSPICION OF CRIME

LEAs and BGs become aware of, or are alerted to, a suspected waste-related crime. This may result from community reports, general monitoring of high-risk areas, or a request from a public prosecutor to investigate a specific location.

FORMAL INVESTIGATION AFTER A PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENT

Once a potential site or person is identified as possibly being involved in a waste crime, a preliminary assessment is conducted to verify the suspicion. EMERITUS offers a wide range of services to support this step—through **drones, waste trafficking detection, change analysis, area monitoring**, and more.

FORMAL INVESTIGATION AND EVIDENCE GATHERING

After the preliminary assessment confirms the presence of illegal waste activity, the investigation enters the formal phase. The aim here is to gather a comprehensive body of evidence admissible in court, either for prosecution or regulatory action. This phase must be carried out in line with evidentiary standards to ensure legal validity. It typically involves detailed inspections to identify waste types and assess environmental damage. EMERITUS services can significantly enhance the efficiency and accuracy of this process by leveraging on **satellite images, AI algorithms, sensors and drones missions**.

KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

NOTIFICATION TO INVESTIGATED SUBJECTS

Notifying subjects who are suspected or proven responsible of facilitating, or directly illegally storing waste in an illicit manner is a critical part of the investigation process – especially as to prevent further environmental damage. At this stage, data and evidences produced through EMERITUS services can be used to support the notification to the investigated subject of the pollution and can be supplementary material in potential cease and desist notices, or official warnings.

REPORTING OF EVIDENCE TO CORRESPONDING PROSECUTORIAL BODY

Once a formal investigation has been completed, EMERITUS can support the reporting of the investigation's outcome to prosecutors and or its admission to court. Indeed, the **data repository, and project function of EMERITUS** can provide a central location to store a range of data, from different instruments and sources, which can be used to construct final reports and cases for further action, to support the reporting of the any of the four environmental crimes to the corresponding prosecutorial body. This would include data from the **Drone Control service, the Waste Trafficking Detection service, the 3D Mapping Service, Waste Site Expert Report, The Water Pollution Detection Service, The Air Quality Service**, among others. The data produced by EMERITUS technologies are stored in EMERITUS' secure database, accessible only by authorised credentials and **two-factor authentication**. The data repository provides records on which users have accessed, or downloaded, the data produced by the services, allowing it to meet evidentiary requirements. In conclusion, EMERITUS and its services not only has the potential to alert and warn the suspect of the hazards, but it also plays a significant role in the legal and regulatory processes. Its importance lies in its ability to provide accurate, real-time data that is crucial for both immediate public health responses and long-term environmental justice and compliance.

KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

Training programme

Taking into consideration fast developing technologies, there is a high need for the agents to be trained about its aims, use and application in their work. Based on an initially conducted needs assessment, the **EMERITUS training** was developed encompassing both:

THEORETICAL ASPECTS:

Emerging trends about environmental crime.

Forensic Science to ensure a sound management of physical and digital evidence.

PRACTICAL ASPECTS:

Novel Technological solutions available to support investigation.

Practical application of EMERITUS Platform and corresponding investigation protocol (leveraging on the participation of technical experts).

Needs Assessment revealed that each country has different levels of training in the area of environmental crime. Many receive training, but more on general and basic levels, covering theoretical knowledge. Needs Assessment showed that many participants expressed interest to receive training in legislative matters (definitions of environmental crimes, codification of legislation, damage calculations etc). Many were interested in gathering evidence techniques, improvement of the forensic skills. In addition, many pointed out the need for the use of drones, satellite information, remote sensing, GIS, geo-profiling, thermographic investigations etc.

KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

Training programme

Approach for theoretical and practical knowledge transfer

Training activities constitute a core part of EMERITUS and its pathway towards impact: indeed the International Training Programme was tailored on the actual needs of LEAs/BGs, as collected under the initial phases of the co-creation process (WP1, WP2), and it aimed at concretely empowering operators to understand the nature, peculiarities, trends and regulations related to environmental crimes (theoretical part = 16h), while providing them with hands-on-exercises experience (via simulation exercises and demonstration at Calvarina ex- military base = 24h) on the use of the technologies integrated by EMERITUS as well as on protocol implementation and interforce collaboration.

International Training Center for Authorities and Leaders (CIFAL in spanish) certified the attendance to the full course. The training plan used a combination of theory and practice covering each stage of the analysis, design, implementation and evaluation phases of training, as well as inclusive and gender-sensitive training design. It included conceptual summaries, interactive exercises, practice activities, reflection questions, case studies and visual aids to create an engaging and impactful learning experience.

Training plan

To facilitate access to the certificate, we will carried out a training itinerary. For example:

01

Structure the training in 6 modules of 3h. each (18 hours total)

02

Each person chooses the modules that are of interest to them

03

If the sum of the hours of the completed modules add up to 8h. (or more), they would get the certificate of completion

The objective is that each person focuses on the training that interests them and can obtain the certificate that adds value to their training.

At the end of the course, Trainers are equipped with the knowledge necessary to design and implement effective and impactful training events to further disseminate acquired knowledge. They gain a deep understanding of unique approach to training design, which is grounded in principles of adult learning theory and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

Community of practice

To achieve its objectives, EMERITUS has created an initial network of external stakeholders, the **Community of Practice (CoP)**, whose members were invited to participate in information sharing activities (also through a dedicated newsletter), working groups and showcase events. These events aimed at sharing knowledge from the project results regarding mainly:

PROTOCOL CO-CREATION

Through the user need assessment activities CoP members contributed to the Creation of a baseline investigation protocol to guide law enforcement agencies to harmonize their investigation approaches.

GEO INTELLIGENCE PLATFORM DEVELOPMENT AND INTEGRATION

CoP members were invited to a series of showcases events both in presence and on-line where they were informed on the EMERITUS platform technologies application and integration, the types of inputs used and outputs generated. They contributed in providing feedbacks related on further purposes the platform can be used for and how other technologies could be integrated to improve the tool according to their expertise and experiences.

OPERATIONAL TRAINING AND TESTING OF THE EMERITUS INTEGRATED SOLUTION

CoP members contributed in the designing of training programme for Police Authorities and other security practitioners focused on environmental crimes investigation. They were invited to testing activities related to the EMERITUS platform and protocol in a semi-controlled environment, based on 4 defined use cases for the monitoring and assessment of the integrated protocol, components' integration and platform operational application.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION AND ROADMAP

CoP members contributed by elaborating a set of policy recommendation and a roadmap for the protocol uptake and its standardization, recalling the need for a medium to long-term vision on how the European Union could better and timely prevent and detect environmental crime incidents, strengthening its legal and regulatory framework'

USE CASES

UC1

WATER CONTAMINATION DETECTION AND PREDICTION (SPAIN – LOCAL CASE)

CETAQUA AND POLICÍA LOCAL MÁLAGA

PARTNERS

The Guadalhorce is the main river of Malaga (Province of Spain) regarding river length and basin area, which eventually flows in the Mediterranean. The river mouth is made up of two branches, one of them artificial, built due to continuous flooding. Between both arms can be found a natural wetland which constitutes the Natural Park of Guadalhorce, close by is located the city of Malaga. **This natural and protected area is not exempt of illegal discharges, due to the river running through Industrial sites, Malaga airport and the golf club Real Guadalhorce.** In this context, it is quite usual to detect pollution plumes in the Natural Park during the year. The official police responsible for safeguarding Natural Park environment is the **MOM unit associated to the Municipal Police of Malaga.**

OBJECTIVES

- Develop a novel sensing system based on the concept of virtual sensor and capable of detecting contaminations events.
- Develop a model to predict the pollution plumes along the river and the Natural Park according to contamination measurements collected upstream from Natural Park.
- Predict the timeline of pollution plume in the river, in case of illegal discharge, providing to the MOM unit enough time and information to prepare and implement mitigation actions to reduce the impact of illegal discharges in the Natural Park.

IMPACTS

01

Enhance capability to classify type of contaminants and contaminant sources.

02

Supporting near-to-real-time event detection and capability to detect responsibilities.

03

Prediction downstream contaminant concentration (mitigation actions proposal).

04

Illegal discharge source localization.

TARGET TECHNOLOGIES

- > AI algorithms
- > Multispectral cameras
- > Quality and hydraulic water sensors
- > Virtual sensor based on commercial real time sensors
- > Edge AI approaches

RESULTS

R1 - Geo-located geoJSON notification system, providing information of the type of event detected, the timestamp and the location. [I1; I2; I4]

R2 - Prediction models, producing a description of the details and the expected evolution of the episode (detected components, candidate source of contamination, expected concentration over time, predicted trajectory). [I1; I3; I4]

UC2

INDUSTRIAL STORAGE CENTRES MONITORING (ITALY – LOCAL NATIONAL COORDINATION)

PARTNERS

LOCAL POLICE OF TURIN, N.O.E. - ECOLOGICAL
OPERATIONAL UNIT OF CARABINIERI, GMV, LOGIKERS,
POLITECNICO DI TORINO

According to the data of Piedmont Environmental Protection Agency (ARPA Piemonte), the environmental crimes identified and reported to the Public Prosecutor's Office in 2019 by the Protection and Surveillance Service of the Northwest Piedmont Territorial Department were a total of 163. At national level, according to ISTAT reports, the legal proceedings for environmental violations were 10.320 in 2016, with most of the alleged violations concerning waste management (8.792 proceedings) and wastewater (1.636), including 170 procedures for the unauthorized transport of waste and 164 for the organized traffic of waste. Local authorities operate on the territory, carrying out investigations, monitoring and inspections in complex and dangerous environments, to collect evidence for initiating criminal proceedings or launching preliminary investigations.

A sound coordination and exchange of information between the responsible LEAs at Local and National level (i.e. Turin Police, Carabinieri - NOE) is essential to ensure a quick and effective monitoring of and reaction to environmental crimes.

OBJECTIVES

Identifying and standardizing the data, both geospatial and informative, and the processing workflow useful for local operator to investigate waste crime.

Define simulation scenario for data acquisition, analysis, testing, training and validation.

Use of EMERITUS Platform tools for automatic and semi-automatic classification of VHR satellite and drone dataset exploiting ML/IA as well as R&D activities for fine-tuning the aforementioned tools and exploiting GALILEO constellation for robust positioning.

IMPACTS

01

Enhanced detection and investigation capability.

02

Improved capability to coordinate local-national investigative efforts.

TARGET TECHNOLOGIES

- › LOGIKERS ad hoc developed data gathering prototype based on a drone able to fly automatically on a selected area and perform air and radiation analysis.
- › Automatic and semi-automatic classification and detection algorithms
- › Sensors for atmosphere and ground analysis
- › AI-driven data analysis to satellite imagery

RESULTS

R1 - Extended results datasets (video footage, pictures, raw visual evidence, geospatial data, orthomage datasets, digital surface model datasets, thematic map datasets, etc.) and evidence on recurrences of modus operandi (KeyCrime results).

R2 - LOGIKERS ad hoc developed data gathering prototype.

R3 - UAV-based Land Cover classification

UC3

CROSS-BORDER ILLEGAL TRAFFICKING VIA LAND (ROMANIA & MOLDOVA)

PARTNERS

GMV RO, Romanian Border Police, Moldovian Police, Moldovian Inspectorate for Environmental Protection, Romanian National Environmental Guard, INESC TEC.

Since 2007, the implementation of waste management measures in Romania has encountered several difficulties, one of the most important being the abolition of existing landfills and the delay in the construction of ecological landfills, so that currently there are still 44 landfills to be closed. The rudimentary waste management infrastructure and limited access to waste collection services lead to the uncontrolled dumping of waste of any kind.

Concerning the problem of waste trafficking, representatives of the Romanian Environmental Guard are estimating that a turnover of 550 million euros a year is obtained from the black market of waste.

In 2021, Romania has discovered as many illegal shipments of garbage as in the last five years. Romania is mainly a waste importer, most of its waste arriving from Japan but also European countries such as Germany, Belgium, Netherlands, Italy or the United Kingdoms. The lack of selection of waste to be reused in different industries is the reason for the increase in illegal imports of garbage from other states.

Illegal waste import to Romania enters through almost any type of border crossing, except air. Remains of products are transported in unloaded containers in seaports such as Constanța, transported by barges – entering through the ports on the Danube, or by trucks entering through the border check points.

Unlike Romania, which is mainly an import country, in Moldavia waste trafficking includes both waste imports and exports, the main exportation country being Ukraine, while the country of origin for waste importation being Russia.

The illegal waste transports that were detected by the Moldavian Border Police consist of mainly ferrous and non-ferrous metal waste, but also hazardous materials such as unrecycled medical waste and white mercury. Until August 2021 alone, almost 140 garbage containers destined to enter the country were discovered by the Romanian border police together with GNM.

OBJECTIVES

Documenting and describing the current illegal waste import/export activities in Romania and Moldavia and selecting the most suitable sites for implementing the pilot case.

Exploit satellite data and remote sensing monitoring for detailed analysis of landfills, detection of illegal dumping areas and characterization of wastes.

Monitoring over time detected landfills (spatial extension & volumetric changes). Detection of patterns related to waste illegal trafficking.

IMPACTS

01

Automatization of the capability to detect landfill and characterization of waste type.

02

Identification of correlations between evolution patterns and illegal waste imports.

TARGET TECHNOLOGIES

- > Satellite data (Landsat MultiSpectral Scanner - MSS)
- > Thematic Mapper (TM) or Sentinel-2 MSI
- > AI (Deep Learning through conventional neural networks applied on Very High Resolution images)
- > Advanced analytics
- > Photointerpretation and photogrammetric techniques (stereophotogrammetry)
- > Multispectral imagery for vegetation indices' analysis

RESULTS

R1 - Near-real time waste detection service based on medium resolution free of charge Sentinel 2.

R2 - Sentinel 2 waste detection datasets based on multiple countries – Romania, Moldavia, Hungary and Greece at different time spans.

R3 - Demonstration of robust results with CNN architectures on low resolution features such as waste dumps with the help of modern segmentation approaches (architecture, loss function, dataset imbalance problem).

UC4

IDENTIFICATION OF ILLEGAL WASTE SITES AND LINK WITH TRAFFICKING (GREECE – NATIONAL & CROSS-BORDER)

PARTNERS

Hellenic Police, Air & Space Evidence and KEMEA

Greece has had a long-standing problem with illegal waste sites and licence breaches at authorised/permited waste sites. In 2014 it received a €40 million fine and a penalty payment of €42.8 million for each six-month period of delay in taking necessary measures from the European Court.

OBJECTIVES

Detect Illegal Waste Sites (and provide better intelligence on risk), via ASE detection model leveraging ESA Sentinel 2-satellite data to identify potential waste sites.

Check the results against the list of known licenced landfill and used uses very high-resolution satellite Earth observation data (0.30m) to examine in each site that was found.

Detect illegal sites and illegal behaviour at permitted sites using thermal anomaly detection model and satellite data (searching for waste illegally burnt).

Monitoring of exports of wastes for evidence-based inspections, by cross referencing consignment note data (cargos' origin and destination) and identified potentially illegal sites.

IMPACTS

01

Improved capability to identify and classify the risk of illegal waste sites (exploiting the integration of both open sources and VHR satellite data).

02

Improved capability to detect illegal behaviours at permitted sites (and links with other illegal behaviours, e.g. other type of crimes, disposal of different types of waste).

03

Evidence-based inspections and enhanced ex ante preparedness of agents on the field.

TARGET TECHNOLOGIES

- > Satellites (Sentinel 2 satellite data and Very High Resolution data).
- > AI algorithms for illegal sites detection and cross-referencing.

RESULTS

R1 – Map and a table of the latitude and longitude coordinates of all potential landfill sites in selected regions of Greece

R2 – Detailed examination of selected sites providing information such as image of the site using the satellite data, site status (active or historical), type of landfill (fill/materials)

LESSONS LEARNT AND DERIVED RECOMMENDATIONS

Digital Platform

Procurement Processes

Police forces are bound by strict procurement regulations. It is therefore essential to define specific **business models** that align with these frameworks to enable widespread adoption and long-term exploitation of the solution.

Skill Gaps

There is a scarcity of certain specialised competencies within police forces—such as drone pilots. The EMERITUS platform can help bridge these gaps by facilitating access to **external expertise** or offering targeted **training** opportunities.

Facilitating Collaboration

The EMERITUS platform should serve as a **collaborative space** where police forces and civilian experts can interact. This enables the sharing of services and expertise, fostering mutual support in tackling complex environmental crimes.

Scalability through APIs

The EMERITUS platform is designed to be scalable and future-proof. An **API-driven architecture** allows for the gradual integration of new services, ensuring continuous growth and adaptability to emerging needs.

LESSONS LEARNT AND DERIVED RECOMMENDATIONS

Investigation Protocol

Case-by-Case Flexibility

Each environmental crime and waste crime case presents unique characteristics. A rigid, one-size-fits-all investigation protocol appeared not to be a preferable option in terms of effectiveness: protocols must be **adaptable** to accommodate diverse crime types, scenarios and evolving challenges.

Multi-level Coordination

There is a need for improved coordination between local and national authorities, as well as the institutions responsible for investigating environmental crimes. Strengthening this coordination will enhance the overall effectiveness of enforcement efforts. Additionally, **international coordination** is essential to effectively address transnational issues such as waste trafficking.

Dedicated Units

Establishing dedicated departments or units focused specifically on **environmental crime** would ensure more consistent and centralised coordination among relevant institutions. Furthermore, the creation of specialized courts with judges who are experts in environmental and waste crimes would enhance the effectiveness of the justice system in addressing these issues.

Public Reporting Mechanisms

A structured entry point for **citizen reports**, supported by digital tools, can enable quick screening of potential cases. This helps to distinguish relevant notifications from non-actionable ones and improves responsiveness.

LESSONS LEARNT AND DERIVED

Training Programme

European Harmonisation

A harmonised training approach at the European level is essential to ensure consistent knowledge and enforcement practices across member states.

Technical Knowledge

Environmental crimes often involve highly technical issues such as contamination and waste management. It is crucial that law enforcement personnel receive specialised training in these areas.

Cross-Border Training

Joint training initiatives between countries are necessary to strengthen cross-border collaboration and foster mutual understanding in handling environmental crimes.

Awareness of International Regulations

There is limited awareness of international regulations governing environmental crimes. Implementing the EU Directive could provide a framework for harmonised and specialised training, enhancing the technical competence of relevant authorities.

Community of Practice

Sustained Engagement

Ongoing engagement of the experts in the activities are vital for the continued development and relevance of the EMERITUS platform.

Strengthening Co-Creation

Regular engagement reinforces the co-creation methodology, which is central to addressing practical, real-world needs through the platform.

Networking and Collaboration

The Community of Practice offers valuable opportunities for networking, knowledge exchange, and deeper engagement among stakeholders.

ROADMAP AHEAD

Integration of new digital services through API

- The API, developed using FastAPI, serves as a communication layer between the frontend and backend, enabling data transmission and process orchestration.
- It interfaces with a PostgreSQL relational database and supports a wide range of backend services including user management, project and order handling, risk location management, file handling (via S3), logging, commenting, and user monitoring.
- Authentication and authorization are implemented via Keycloak using OAuth2 protocols.
- While most internal endpoints are intentionally excluded from the auto-generated Swagger documentation, endpoints relevant to external partners are included and documented with detailed descriptions of their purpose, request formats, and expected responses.
- Due to the complexity and variety of backend operations, the structure of requests and responses can differ significantly between endpoints.
- The backend also manages external integrations, establishing connections with partner APIs, databases, S3/SFTP storage systems, and orchestrating workloads in Nomad clusters or through selected cloud providers.
- Integration strategies vary: if partner software can be containerized using Docker, it can be seamlessly executed within the existing infrastructure.
- Non-containerized services can also be integrated, though they may require additional effort depending on their packaging and interface requirements.

Replication and follow up projects

EMERITUS welcomes collaboration on replication efforts and follow-up initiatives, such as:

- Definition of a collaborative research and innovation project
- Integration of new software functionalities in the platform
- Replication of the training programme
- Co-hosting of webinar or conferences concerning environmental crimes or technological aspects
- Execution of specific pilots

emeritus

If you are interested in
cooperating with EMERITUS,
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